

Social Innovations for a Circular Built Environment: A Heuristic Framework Based on a Review

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Abstract

In the face of climate change and resource scarcity, the built environment's transition towards circular practices is thought to be inevitable. To foster a transition of any system, not only technological, but also social innovations are needed. Based on a literature review including both scientific and grey literature, this paper thus makes an effort to shed light on the social component of existing innovations for a circular built environment. To that end, a framework is designed using existing classifications and frameworks to help better understand social innovations in the built environment, their similarities and patterns as well as the dynamics that arise from them. It finds that the majority of social innovations for a circular built environment under study tend to focus on the use of materials and buildings, thus narrowing or slowing resource flows, whereas the closing of resource flows seems to be left outside of social structures. As an overarching theme, the article notes that, in this context, circularity is often framed as a social innovation itself, however without being addressed as such.

Author summary

In today's era of climate change and resource scarcity, transitioning towards circular practices in the built environment is crucial. However, this shift requires more than just technological advancements; it necessitates social innovations as well. Our paper delves into the social aspect of existing innovations for a circular built environment by analyzing a range of literature. We developed a framework to better understand these social innovations, their patterns, and the dynamics they create. Our research reveals that many social innovations in this context focus on material and building usage, aiming to slow or narrow resource flows. Interestingly, the closing of resource

loops appears to be less integrated into social structures. Moreover, we observe that while circularity is often presented as a social innovation itself, it's not consistently addressed as such. Our findings highlight the importance of considering both technological and social innovations in fostering a truly circular built environment, offering valuable insights for future research and policy development.

1 Introduction

The construction industry is widely acknowledged to not only account for about 40% of societal resource consumption (1–3), but also to be responsible for 25 – 40 % of global CO₂ emissions(4). A solution to these problems is the shifting of construction processes from linear towards circular activities (e.g. 5,6). Understanding the built environment (BE) as a socio-economic-technical system (7) implies the importance of not only technical but also social innovations (SI) for such a transformation. However, up to now there is little systematic knowledge about which kind of social innovations in the context of circular construction and circular built environment exist and to what extent they can contribute to fostering circular practices in this area.

Against this backdrop, this paper aims to contribute to the state of the art by answering the following research questions:

- 1) Are existing innovations in or for circular construction and circular environment mainly technological, as literature implies? Or are the social factors and benefits merely underrepresented?
- 2) How can we identify SI in the context of the circular transformation of the BE in the interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research?

To do so, the sections in this paper give an overview of the methods used (section 2), followed by the motivation and background (section 3). To assess innovations in the context of a circular BE as to whether they are social innovations, a heuristic framework is proposed in section 4. Insights from a literature search are reviewed in section 5, and put into perspective using the framework of SI in section 6, which also discusses the results. Section 7 gives a conclusion and outlook for possible further research.

2 Methods

A literature review was conducted, using the Web of Science and a two-step search string to gather insights from scientific literature focusing on circularity in the BE and SI in the context of circularity and the Be (cf. Fig 1). After a process of building elaborated search terms including as many relevant keywords as possible, and trying them in the Web of Science, it transpired that a simpler, yet more specific, search term resulted in the best, i. e., most relevant and specific results list. Thus, the search term *TOPIC: ("built environment" OR construction OR "building industry") AND TOPIC: (circularity OR "circular economy" OR (circular AND (flows OR material OR resource*)))* was used to retrieve the data basis for the first part of the review. It was constructed with the goal in mind that most every construction activity as well as the specific term “built environment” should be included as well as many forms of circularity as possible. Every term was searched for in “all fields” (i. e., topic, title, author, publication titles, abstracts, keywords, etc.). Document types were refined to articles and review articles to ensure scientific relevance, and categories were refined to exclude irrelevant categories of publications (e. g. medicine, genetics, computational sciences, etc.). Geographically, the search was not limited, and the timeframe was set to Jan 1, 1900 to Oct 31, 2021 so recent documents would be included as well. The search

process as well as the search terms are shown in Fig 1. The results were then screened for eligibility manually by viewing the title and abstracts, and articles that did not fit the topic were excluded (e.g., articles that focus on the statics of circular steel beams). Subsequently, the result list was fed back into the Web of Science and the search term was extended by *AND TOPIC: ("soci* innovat*" OR (social* AND transformat*) OR ("new ways of" AND (think* OR organiz* OR fram*)) OR social* AND (practice OR initiative OR organiz*))*, which resulted in a list of 74 publications. These were again screened according to the goals of the search and any publications that did not deal with social innovations were excluded. To that end, if an article did not reveal the eligibility by screening title and abstract, the text was screened as well. This resulted in a list of 34 scientific articles that were qualitatively analysed and used to gain the insights in the following. Although the literature review delivers some insights in the scientific landscape concerning circularity in the BE, it does not integrate SI in the greater picture. This may be due to the fact that “social innovation” as a buzzword has not yet marked its place in the scientific perception, and, as Horgan and Dimitrijević (8) point out, there is yet a „limited research pool of examples“ for SI in the BE. However, the literature body (D) provided a number of examples of SI that contribute to a circular BE; based on them, a scoping review was compiled to complement the literature body by further relevant literature that was retrieved by using a snowballing approach researching further scientific and grey literature to pay credit to common approaches in transdisciplinary research as well as practice and integrate “knowledge from various scientific and societal bodies of knowledge” (9). As a starting point for grey literature research the report “Circular Economy in the Built Environment” by the engineering and consulting firm Arup (10) was used, as it lists many innovations in the relevant field that, although mentioned in the literature, have not yet been thoroughly dealt with in peer-reviewed scientific literature. To find additional relevant and recent grey literature, the Google search engine and Google Scholar were used. Using the examples of SI implementing circularity

in parts of the BE as inspiration for the following research, and complementing them with further examples retrieved in the scoping review, resulted in an exemplary list of 20 examples. In and following this exploratory overview, the found SI are classified using a framework designed for that purpose that consists of the definitions for the core concepts of SI, BE, and circularity (cf. section 3) as well as models to compare them coherently (i.e., involved stakeholders and targeted life cycle phase) to point out patterns and exceptionalities (see section 4).

3 Motivation and background

Scientific literature depicts innovations in the context of a circular built environment as mostly technological, business model innovations (e.g. 11,12), or circular innovations (cf. 13). However,

in the interest of an integrated transformation of the BE towards circularity, and, thus, sustainability, the social factor cannot be ignored, which is why this paper seeks to shine light on this up until now underrepresented factor of sustainability transitions in the BE.

To do so, as a conceptual starting point, this work defines the BE as the *object of interest* for achieving sustainability targets. Circularity therefore represents the overall *goal* of achieving changes in the BE, while SI are recognized as a key *instrument* to reach that goal. The following paragraphs give an overview of the state of the art of science of these three concepts and illuminate their interdependencies.

Social innovations

Definitions for social innovation (SI) range from very narrow to very broad understandings (14) that allow for a plethora of non-technical – “as a complement to technological innovation” (ibid.) – and, depending on the context, business as well as inherently social innovations to be perceived as such (15).

A commonly used definition for SI is that they need to be “social in both their ends and their means” (15–17), with *social in their ends* meaning the “improving of societal well-being” (14,18). Moving beyond the teleological approach of this widely accepted definition, this article refers to social innovations as “new ways of doing (practices, technologies, material commitments), organizing (rules, decision-making, modes of governance), framing (meaning, visions, imaginaries, discursive commitments) and knowing (cognitive resources, competence, learning, appraisal)” as a classificatory framework (cf. 19–22), defining “SI as a process of changing social relations” (22), “explicitly referring to socio-*material* relations that connect ideas, objects, activities and people” (ibid.;

cf. also 19,23). Similarly, Wittmayer et al. (14) explicitly “move beyond simplistic notions of ‘improvement’” through SI, and, even farther, “beyond instrumentalism”, proposing a variety of considerations to inform a broader imagination and strategizing of structural changes”. This perspective thus not only comprises social endeavours, but also “innovations that are not only good for society but also enhance society’s capacity to act” (16), including both today’s society and future generations. Following that understanding, an open mind is to be kept recognize an SI as such; thus, examples for illustration are given where needed to make understanding the perspective easier. For instance, *framing* disused industrial buildings not as ruins that need to be demolished, but as spaces of possibilities to (adaptively) reuse them opens the opportunities to build residential space and communities using significantly less virgin resources and emitting less CO₂ in the process.

Often, SI projects cannot be contributed to one of the dimensions of *new ways of doing, organising, framing, or knowing* alone. For example, cooperative buying initiatives (cf. Appendix 2) include the reshaping of relationships among the users of the houses – from neighbours to co-owners that take shared responsibility for their shared property (*organising*) – as well as new perceptions and imaginaries (*framing*) of the used space as a community and social space instead of an exclusive, private and secluded personal space. Another example is the establishment of (certified) construction material reuse platforms which (a) support and provide knowledge about reuse potentials (*knowing*), (b) introduce a third party between supply and demand (*organising*), and (c) potentially increase trust in material quality and fight the waste image of reuse materials (*framing*).

Some SI have a bigger impact on dominating societal practices than others. A SI that “challenges, alters or replaces dominant institutions in the social context” is referred to as a *transformative social innovation* (TSI) (21,24). Such innovations have also been called game changers (25) that have the potential to scale up and thereby changes prevailing practices in such a lasting way that

they could be generally accepted and reinforced by institutions and laws, i.e., fundamentally change society.

The circular built environment

The built environment (BE) in its physical sense is defined as the anthropogenic (urban) environment, i.e., buildings and infrastructure in use, as well as larger settlement structures made up of those elements (e. g. blocks, neighborhoods, etc.) including urban green and blue spaces (26–28). It is characterized by its durability, or “obduracy”, that “is regarded as a key barrier to sustainable urban transformation” (27) in that it hinders transitions in a middle-term timeframe if it cannot be adapted to changed societal requirements and lifestyles. Thus, staying in the system-theoretical perspective, a systemic change is needed for a long-term transition of the BE. All the more necessary it is to consider sustainable – circularity – practices not only in new construction but also in the perceived end-of-life of buildings; for instance, energetic retrofitting or adaptive reuse of former industrial or residential buildings.

Van der Leer et al. (7) understand the BE as a socio-ecological-technical system (SETS) consisting of “(at least) [...] a physical system, made up of buildings linked by [...] infrastructure, and a human system made up of people, movement, interaction and activity”. Consistently, Nielsen and Farelly (27) see the city as a “socio-spatial dialectic, whereby the built environment is produced by society, whilst also influencing the actions and decisions of society”. Consequently, technical innovations alone cannot create the systemic change needed to transition conventional building practices and utilization toward sustainable – and, in particular, circular – practices (29) but societal and behavioral approaches are just as crucial to that end (6,30).

Shifting “traditional” linear BE and resource management practices towards a maximum of *circularity* – i.e., in a basic understanding, maximizing the number of times a resource is used, reused, and recycled before being discarded (31,32) – by re-organising the planning process along the BE value chain, i.e., keeping track of the materials, taking care of them being used in a way that they can be extracted and separated after the use phase, and subsequently recovering and reusing them, contributes to a substantial reduction of need of virgin materials as well as energy (33).

The *circular economy* (CE) “is an industrial system that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design” (5), and is thus viewed as “a tremendous opportunity to transform our economy and make it more sustainable” (34). As any economy is a complex system in itself, a systemic change towards circularity is needed to transition to a circular economy. As Foster (33) points out, “a CE must be embedded in a social structure that promotes human well-being for all within the biophysical limits of the planet Earth.” Thus, SI that contribute to the *circularity* of the system’s single components or sub-systems potentially contribute to circular economy in the BE (32,35)

Pomponi and Moncaster (30) call the CE a “new paradigm [that is] now gaining momentum” and enables decoupling growth from resource consumption, which has been focused on by sustainability research for a long time (36,37).

To classify different strategies of circular business models, Bocken et al. (38) build on existing literature and introduce the categorization of those strategies into slowing, closing, and narrowing resource flows. They summarize the strategies as follows:

“[...] ‘slowing’ is about prolonged use and reuse of goods over time, through design of long life goods and product life extension, whereas closing loops is about reuse of materials through recycling. Narrowing loops is about reducing resource use associated with the product and production process.” (38)

Thus, they are essentially promoting a more efficient resource use in any stage – production, use, and end of life and making positive use of the buildings’ “obduracy”. In the context of the built environment, this classification describes practices of, for instance, (adaptive) reuse or (energetic) retrofitting of buildings (*slowing*, i.e., prolonging a building’s lifetime); the use of reclaimed and recycled buildings materials like concrete (*closing* resource loops), or off-site prefabrication of building parts in order to reduce transportation and construction waste, thus reorganising manufacturing and construction processes (new ways of doing) (*narrowing*) (cf. also 7).

4 Proposing a framework for identifying social innovations for circularity in the built environment

As a basis for a comprehensive assessment of innovations found through the literature review, a heuristic framework is proposed by integrating existing frameworks and classification approaches (cf. Table 1). The framework intends to help assess if an innovation is indeed a social innovation by referring to its characteristics as well as social benefits. Moreover, to point out patterns and correlations in order to support decision-making, the stakeholders involved and the respective life cycle phases of the building are plotted as well. Each SI found in the literature research has thus been categorized and examined for several characteristics.

Table 1: Framework bases: Questions, categories, and frameworks used.

Question	Category	Framework
How is it a social innovation?	New ways of doing, organising, framing, and knowing (plus sub-categories, cf. Section 3); social benefits	(16,17,21,23)
How does it contribute to circularity?	Slowing, closing, narrowing resource flows	(38)

Does it have potential to fundamentally transform societal habits on the long run?	„social innovation that <i>challenges, alters or replaces</i> dominant institutions in the social context”	(21,24)
What are the stakeholders involved?	<i>Users, market actors, governance</i>	
Where in the life cycle does it need to be considered?	<i>Design, take, make, use, dispose, store</i>	(39)

The results from using this framework on innovations found in literature are shown in Table 2 and interpreted in the following. It presents a non-comprehensive list of social innovations in the context of the BE, that contribute to its circularity, involve different stakeholder groups and target a variety of life cycle phases.

Table 2: Social innovations for a circular built environment, categorized using a heuristic framework.

Label	Contribution to circularity	How is it an SI		Potential to transform prevailing practices	Stakeholders involved			Life cycle phase(s)					references	
		New ways of...	Social benefit		Users	Market actors	Governance	Design	Take	Make	Use	Dispose		
3D printing of buildings and building parts	narrowing	doing	implementation of technologies: apart from the technology behind it, 3D printing enables locally individual solutions as well as enhances communication between users and user groups, thus enabling open collaboration	empowerment of users; overcoming of "traditional" design guidelines		●		●		●				(40,41)
Adaptive Re-use	slowing	framing	Meaning, visions: Reframing the building and its use; alternative perception of buildings put out of use (possibilities instead of ruins), resulting in new user practices	Promotes social wellbeing, new job opportunities, social inclusion and sense of community	●						●	●		(42–45)
		Doing	Practices: Alternative re-use of the respective building											
Building Information Modeling	narrowing	doing	implementation of technologies: interlinked planning method allowing for all stakeholders to collaborate and contribute in any stage of planning; also allows for detailed tracking of changes and material use	Industry-wide collaboration	●	●		●		●				(46–48)
Building Material Exchange Platforms	closing	knowing	cognitive resources: Providing knowledge about availability and acquisition of used or excess construction material	accessibility of (affordable) materials; stimulating collaboration		●			●					(40,49)
		Framing	Meaning: perceiving used materials as materials instead of waste											

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Cooperative Building or Buying	narrowing	organising	decision making: Changes the ways building and buying processes (esp. decision-making) are communicated and thus organised: co-production, co-operation	community building; fighting loneliness; affordable and secure housing	provide social participation to lower-income users, thus empowering them; transition the focus from ownership to (shared) use	●												(40,50-52)
Design for Disassembly / Deconstruction	slowing	doing	material commitment: "The deconstruction process essentially changes the traditional waste management process"	Affordable building / module sourcing; encourages sharing or using used modules	Abolish users' dependency on market actors, thus empowering the user; shift private construction to own responsibility		●		●									(40,46,47,53-55)
		framing	changing the perception of used building parts and materials from waste to usable materials															
Design for Manufacture and Assembly	slowing	doing	practices: new building practices	Reduction of parts count, thus ability to DIY for the users: empowerment of users	changing planning and building practices - rethinking the building as a whole; Abolish users' dependency on market actors, thus empowering the user; shift private construction to own responsibility	●	●		●		●							(56,57)
Flexible Design	slowing	framing	Imaginaries: includes several possibilities of a changed user concept after the original use phases, e.g. by adding or breaking down walls to change apartment layouts	flexibility facing changing situations and realities			●		●				●	●				(10,44,46,58,59)
Individual Sustainability Competences	narrowing	knowing	Competences: offering knowledge and competences to a broader part of society and as a common part of engineering studies	availability of more/new knowledge	By providing the competences and skills needed, a new generation of engineers can "take over" the construction sector in the long term, focusing on sustainable construction instead of traditional practices.				●		●							(47,49,58,60-62)
Legislation & Regulation	Slowing, closing, narrowing	organising	Rules: top-down approach to incentivise or enforce more sustainable decision making	Encouraging conscious decisions; facilitate education; foster innovation					●	●	●							(7,40,46,47,63-65)
Modular Building and Prefabrication	narrowing	doing	Practices: new building practices that make up a faster, cheaper, and more efficient building process	affordability of building; flexibility facing changing situations, demands and needs, and realities			●		●		●							(44,47,49,66,67)
Product-Service Systems	narrowing	framing	Meaning: change the way products are perceived - switching the focus from ownership to the service they provide	flexibility; affordability; "focus on customer needs instead of physical products"	provide social participation to lower-income users, thus empowering them; transition the focus from ownership to use	●	●				●	●	●					(12,13,49,68,69)
Regenerative Design	slowing	framing	Imaginaries: "The objective of [regenerative] development [...] is to create a future where people can live in mutually supportive symbiosis with their social and biophysical environment" (70) (<i>imaginaries</i>)	Enhancing urban environment, thus public health			●		●									(70-73)
Reuse and Recycling of Building Components and Elements	closing	doing	material commitment: the perception of used building materials not as waste but as usable materials	affordability; conducive to creativity; creation of highly and low-qualified jobs			●			●	●							(44,47,48,55,61,67,74-76)
Regenerative Sustainability	slowing	framing	Meaning: changing the perspective on the BE from single buildings to a system, and envisioning it as a part of a sustainable environment: "Regenerative sustainability [...] stands for further development and a paradigmatic change in the consideration of sustainability" (77)	Enhanced public health, social equity			●		●									(77)
Remote Work	narrowing	doing	Practices: a new lifestyle: "teleworking may offer opportunities for autonomous and flexible co-ordination"	flexibility in daily life: "reshaping urban form to shift to more vibrant"	"a form of organisational change, eventually including a particular process innovation (from work organised in traditional offices established/provided by the	●	●						●					(65,78)

			of work and private life as well as use of time [...]"	and distributed, multi-functional, mixed-use and medium-density forms that helps diversify the economy"	employer to an organisation including work from remote locations)"													
Selective Disassembly	slowing	doing	material commitment: Selective disassembly is a form of Urban Mining: perception of used building materials not as waste but as usable materials															(79)
Sharing Economy	Slowing, narrowing	doing	material commitment: "Sharing economy practices promote the optimal allocation of under-utilized and idle resources, such as construction materials, labour and machinery equipment, in each unique construction project" (80)	affordability; community building; building of networks														(11,80,81)
Tiny Houses	narrowing	doing	Practices: frugal use of residential space, focusing on efficiency, sufficiency, and sometimes mobility	affordability; frugality; flexibility	new way of using residential space - going from "the more the better" to dealing with as little (space) as possible - frugality as a lifestyle; make affordable living space available to more people; empower users/dis-empower investors													(82)
Urban Mining	closing	doing	material commitment: the perception of used building materials not as waste but as usable materials															(46,63,76,83-85)
		Framing	Meaning: Urban Mining is an expression of the "societal transformation towards closed material loops" and the "increasing importance of technospheric stocks of secondary resources" (85)															

As not every innovation in the context of the BE can be argued to be an SI, there is a need to clearly define what characteristics need to be present and what excludes innovations from this overview. To that end, the definition of a social innovation Pel et al. (22) developed was used. A special focus was placed on solutions to societal problems and changing social contexts (59) as well as on changing relations between actors, new practices, and business models. To stay true to the idea of circularity of the BE, practices that primarily entail the recycling of material from other cycles (open loop recycling) were not listed. Instead, the focus was put on strategies that strive to keep construction materials in the BE (closed loop recycling) (cf. 86).

5 Innovations, social innovations and circularity in the context of the built environment

The number of publications on the topics of circularity or CE and the BE has been rising exponentially over the last few years. The common view in literature is that, although there is already much awareness in science as well as in practice of the importance of implementing circularity in the BE, there is much research yet to be done on the emerging topic of CE in the BE, and several of the review articles found specific SIs without mentioning the term *social innovation* (mostly reuse or recycling of construction materials), such as modular building, Design for Disassembly, sharing economy, product-service systems (e.g., leasing of building parts) (49,68,87–89), or one or several circularity strategies (R-strategies: *Refuse, rethink, reduce, reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, recycle, recover*) according to Potting et al. (90), as well as the need for changed perceptions and stakeholder relationships (68,88). The initial general finding, however, was that most of the scientific attention in this context has been lying on construction and demolition (C&D) waste management, which included but not necessarily focused on recycling (68,87,91).

It is interesting to note that several of the articles talk about CE, or rather the process of the implementation of circular practices, as an SI in itself, framing it as a rethinking of construction (77,92) or a possibility to “educate and empower individuals at the grassroots to become engaged in sustainable practices” (93), which essentially makes them transformative social innovations (cf. 24). Rakhshan et al. (55) find that “from a social perspective, positive perception and willingness of the stakeholders such as clients [...], designers [...] and contractors [...] to integrate reused components into their projects are determining”, addressing the need to changed material commitments

of the stakeholders from community and market. Hjaltadóttir and Hild (47) emphasize the necessity of stakeholder cooperation and add the need of guidance from policymakers, not only by issuing legislation, but also by making knowledge easily accessible “through networks of stakeholders across different departments and organisations” (94). The availability and transfer of knowledge to practitioners, such as engineers and contractors, is crucial for the transition towards a circular construction industry (61). These ideas align to the debate on the *circular society* (cf. 95,96), a narrative that puts social problems to the center of CE models and “acknowledge[s] the significant social changes required for CE transformations” (96), and “is going beyond growth, technology and market-based solutions”, but instead “frames transitions to circularity as a profound social-ecological transformation” (95). It thus applies a systemic point of view of not only ecosystem or resource cycles but all cycles relevant to society (cf. 97).

Applying CE principles to construction or existing building stock is believed to bring along social benefits such as empowerment, inclusion, or new jobs (44,74,75,93). However, the general focus of publications dealing with a CE in construction has been on sustainable construction, i.e., resource or energy efficiency. A tool that has proven to be efficient in that matter is eco-labeling or guidelines for circular buildings, such as LEED, DGNB, BREEAM, WELL, or Cradle 2 Cradle (77) that also rely on strong soft skills (i.e., communication, coordination, and collaboration) as well as “green skills” (i.e., technical knowledge) on the project managers’ side, which are “necessary, complementary, and mutually supportive” (60), thus indicating individual sustainability consequences to be important to the transition towards a sustainable BE (cf. 60).

Several articles call for more top-down involvement in the form of regulation, incentives, and exemplary function to promote and encourage more circularity engagement in the market (46,47,63,94,98). Other authors found that policies incentivize practices that are considered separately (e.g., construction material exchanges, urban mining, selective disassembly/demolition)

(99,100), focusing on closing the loop, i.e., reusing construction materials in construction instead of downcycling / landfilling (99,101). However, legislature and regulations, although mentioned quite frequently (7,40,46,47,63–65), cannot be generalized. Possibilities range from recycling quotas imposed on new constructions, guarantee and warranty aspects of secondary building materials, to building permits for buildings using new technologies, and the retrofitting and reuse of heritage buildings, thus potentially contributing to all circularity aspects.

6 Results and discussion

Anchoring innovations in the social innovation framework

To coherently assess the innovations in the context of the BE found in literature, a heuristic framework has been designed using existing definitions and frameworks from the scientific literature. In classifying SI in this framework, patterns are displayed that open up themes and gaps, thus providing grounds for future research.

During the research process any innovation found was questioned as to whether it fits into the definition compiled in section 3.1. In doing so, the authors made an effort to identify the primary SI dimension according to Pel et al. (22) to classify the SI, although several of the listed SI actually combine different approaches. For instance, cooperative building incorporates the sharing economy mind-set, and a number of the technological approaches, like Design for Disassembly (DfD), Design for Manufacture and Assembly (DfMA), and 3D printing of buildings work better when using software like Building Information Modeling (BIM) to keep track of materials etc. (cf. e.g. ,102); the same goes for the social benefits brought about by the SI. Similarly, some of the SI involve several of the life cycle phases. It is to no surprise that SI including new construction practices, i.e., target

the make phase, often also rely on specific design methods (e.g., 3D printing of buildings requires appropriate planning; so do DfMA and modular building and prefabrication), and for cooperative buying of out-of-use industrial spaces to turn into residential space it is necessary to re-frame those spaces from “ruins” to “possible residential space”. However, the primary SI dimension here is the new way of organising in a group that uses the space. Using the framework can give an overview of all the different dimensions the SI touch on, thus highlighting the ambiguity and ambivalence inherent to the concept, which can be enhanced by the variety of actors involved in starting the innovation projects.

In reviewing the framework, a few points stand out as striking (cf. Fig 2):

- More than half of the innovations listed can be attributed to *new ways of doing* – and of those, most are new practices in use or construction processes. The major part of these is narrowing resource flows – i.e., more efficient use of resources (construction materials, existing buildings, and space), indicating that individual consumer decisions and preferences are crucial to the sustainable design and use of the built environment. This insight also suggests that a rise of awareness and education regarding consumerism, sustainable choices, and sustainable alternatives and designs are valuable tools in the transition towards circularity.
- It is mostly new practices and new ways of framing, i.e., changed imaginaries of secondary building materials and existing spaces that might be reused, that are attributed to slowing resource flows. Again, this indicates the importance of education for both professionals (i.e., architects, engineers and designers) and users to facilitate a collective rethinking of resources.
- Market actors are involved in the majority of the innovations listed, followed by users. This indicates that although the demand is an important factor, the market’s willingness to give in to this trend is crucial for a circular economy. This is supported by the emphasis on the design phase, that largely relates to professionals (i.e., architects, engineers, or specialist planners)

and is arguably the life cycle phase that will shape the future's BE, thus laying the foundation for a truly circular BE.

Fig 2: Graphical overview of the exemplary list of social innovations including their different dimensions, stakeholders involved, and life cycle phases targeted. Source: Own depiction.

It is to be noted that the classification of circular innovations as social innovations can at times be blurry and needs to be constantly reviewed. Feeding into this debate is the possibility of calling any innovation that contributes to circularity an SI, which bases on the notion that circularity in itself contributes to social well-being by helping secure the environment for future generations.

Sauvé et al. (103) attribute social objectives to sustainable development, but classify the CE as a “model of production and consumption” that follows ecological and economic objectives but not social ones, while Geissdoerfer et al. (104) found that, although being a precondition for sustainability, CE is not necessarily to be equated with sustainability.

Limitations to the study

The study is subject to some limitations inherent to the methods: because of the chosen set of keywords, the scope of the scientific literature review is rather small. As mentioned, however, a bigger keyword range did not produce a more distinct results list, which is why it was decided to stick with variations of the focused topics, SI, BE, and circularity. As it is, a very big share of the list did not refer to the topics aimed at but employed the search terms in different contexts. This lack of scope has been tried to be remedied by complementing the literature review by a scoping review that, employing a snowballing approach and including both scientific and grey literature, helped to overcome the aforementioned methodological limitations.

Some of the SI approaches need to be viewed carefully as they can be ambiguous: The example of the sharing economy sheds light on the need to describe SI types in detail, as the term can mean different versions of the SI: (a) sharing economy in the make-phase, i.e., peer-to-peer (or business-to-business) equipment rental and sharing practices, concepts or designs among project stakeholders and other companies, using digital platforms that “can promote internal and external sharing practices” (80). Li et al. (80) also emphasize the positive sustainability effects of internal sharing practices, i.e., sharing practices among project stakeholders, as opposed to sharing practices with actors outside the project, referring to all three pillars of sustainability – i.e., ecological, economic, and social sustainability –, noting that “external sharing practices can facilitate only

environmental performance”; and (b) sharing economy in the use phase – e.g., shared living, sublet housing (like Airbnb), which can be very different in terms of sustainability criteria. For instance, subletting spaces via Airbnb has been criticized as misappropriation of living space, “feeding speculative real estate investments” (105). A deeper evaluation also shows the importance of considering all three dimensions of sustainability to point out possible sustainability conflicts. An example with a scientifically documented considerable difference between original idea and actual implementation is tiny houses. Although an SI designed to refuse excess and luxury, and minimise land use, literature shows that the actual use of tiny houses does not always correspond to these ideas (82). They are, instead, often used as a second home in addition to traditional homes, and not furnished in a frugal way but luxuriously (ibid.), thus contradicting the sustainability concept of tiny homes. This shows the importance of staying true to the underlying concept of a sustainability strategy, and the need to re-evaluate actions to make sure they still follow the set goals and guidelines. This is also apparent in the goal conflict attributed to the idea of cooperative building: although the concept is undoubtedly sustainable in the social and economic perspective, and many examples implement environmental principles, ecological sustainability is not inherent to the concept, thus has to be incorporated explicitly.

Moreover, explicitly recognizing and labelling transforming potentials, i.e., the potential to challenge, alter, or replace dominant institutions, is not a trivial task, as it is highly dependent on the social or political context it tries to change.

7 Conclusion

Many of the innovations found in scientific as well as practitioners’ literature are focused on as technological, business, or circular innovations. However, upon deeper assessment, many of

them have characteristics attributed to SI: they include new ways of doing, organising, framing or knowing, and produce social benefits.

To help identifying the characteristics of SI, and thus SI in the context of the circular transformation of the BE, we propose a heuristic framework on the basis of an integration of existing classifications and definitions. The framework not only helps identifying SI, but also identifying the stakeholders mainly involved, as well as the life cycle phase(s) targeted. Doing so can help making policy decision about strategies fostering and supporting innovation and SI processes, and, thus, the circular transition of the BE. This aim complies with literature which repeatedly calls for more top-down initiative for circularity in the BE in the form of education, regulation, and incentives to foster circularity initiatives, citing that such interventions in the market are considered to facilitate the transition towards circularity in the BE. The insights from this study imply the same thing: market stakeholders' activities and business models seem to be an important driver of this transition, indicating that facilitating conditions for them – by providing the educational basis, financial incentives, and regulations driving them or hampering traditional construction approaches – will speed up the transition towards circularity in the built environment.

The insights this paper provides open up several strands that could be interesting to look into. For instance, as the CE has repeatedly been referred to as a new paradigm in itself (e.g. 49,104), it might be worthwhile to follow the systems thinking point of view further, including the leverage points concept (106–108) which indicates transcending a society's paradigms as the highest leverage point in a system.

To conclude, it can be said that social innovation for a circular built environment is a highly relevant, yet still understudied field. To answer the questions that prompted this study, an effort has been made to identify existing SIs that contribute to the BE's transition towards circularity. This paper

gives a variety of such innovations, showing that SI are present in relevant scientific and practitioners' literature, however not necessarily explicitly addressed as SI.

Mostly, circularity strategies are mentioned but not evaluated referring to social context. Some publications frame circularity principles, or their implementation process, as an SI in coherence with the *new ways of doing, organising, framing and knowing* framework.

We propose a heuristic framework to coherently classify and compare the SI, thus systematizing the research field to build a basis for future research in this cross-sectional and interdisciplinary area and, by doing so, providing a tool to better understand the influence SI can have on the circularity of the BE.

The review of the scientific literature on SI and BE shows that the common perception of circularity in the BE is more of the physical and technological side. Societal aspects are rarely mentioned, showing that there is still a need for more consideration of the social context when regarding the BE, using as a basis the perception of the BE as a socio-economic-technical system instead of a strictly physical system. Accordingly, SI that are put into motion in the design phase of a building mostly do not put the social factor in the focus but either try to facilitate the construction process or focus on the circularity or regeneration of materials or the whole building by stipulating renewable or recycled materials, or a design that allows for future extensions or dismantling without residue (e.g., DfMA, adaptable architecture); SI that also include deconstruction or the end-of-life of a building in general are either realized from the design phase, or focus on the recycling of building materials (buildings as material banks, selective disassembly).

To follow up on this research, empirical investigation of SI under real world conditions is recommended and intended to determine the influence of spatial and social contexts and derive drivers and barriers from them for selected promising examples. By integrating practice-born experiences

with theoretical findings, this approach aligns the research with common practices in transitions research. Circularity in the built environment is an important and seminal topic, and as this research shows, it can only be reached by employing a combination of technological and social innovations. Thus, gaining as much knowledge about the dynamic of SI contributing to circularity in the BE context is a precondition for transitioning the system of the BE towards resource-saving and sustainable practices.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Author 1: Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Author 2: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Financial disclosure statement

This research is funded by German state and federal funds through the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (<https://ioer.de/en>) as a member of the Leibniz Association (<https://www.leibniz-gemeinschaft.de/en/>). No further external funding was provided. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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